

Studies on Soil Humic Substances. Part I. Fractionation of Fulvic acid and Characterization of Sugar Components

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Manuscript received 11 February 1974 ; accepted 23 May 1974

Fulvic acid was isolated from soil humic substance and the barium salt of it was precipitated at different pH values (4.8, 8.0 and unprecipitated one) to give three fractions which were collected and purified by reprecipitation. Two fractions were shown to be homogeneous by electrophoresis and paper chromatography. Potentiometric titrations were carried out on these three fractions to characterise them. The sugars and amino acids present in them were identified. One of the fractions was enzymatically degraded to give galactose, arabinose and a pentasaccharide. The structure of this oligosaccharide was elucidated.

VARIOUS methods such as paper chromatography and paper electrophoresis¹⁻⁵ have been applied in recent years to fractionate each portion of humus substances. Tyurin⁶ used fractional precipitation to separate fulvic acids into two parts. Forsyth⁷ was able to fractionate fulvic acids with animal charcoal into four parts: a) water-soluble sugars and amino acids, b) phenolic glucosides and tannins, c) a polyuronide probably of bacterial origin and d) a highly nitrogenous fraction containing pentoses and organic phosphates. Humus substances may also be fractionated on Al_2O_3 columns^{8,9} on starch columns¹⁰ with ultracentrifugation¹¹ and by Sephadex gel filtration¹²⁻¹⁶. In the present communication results of the fractionation of fulvic acid into homogeneous materials and characterization of some constituents of one of them are reported.

The soil used for these investigations was obtained from Dehradun, India, and contained 5.5% organic matter. The humus was isolated by extracting the soil with a solution (pH 13) containing sodium hydroxide and sodium pyrophosphate. The extract was acidified to pH 2-3 when the humic acid precipitated out. To the supernatant solution barium chloride was added to convert the fulvic acid into its barium salt and the pH of the solution was slowly raised with a dilute sodium hydroxide solution. When the pH was 4.5-4.8 a buff coloured material (fulvic acid A) precipitated out. It was removed at the centrifuge and on further addition of alkali solution a second precipitate (fulvic acid B) was obtained at pH 8. This was isolated as above. Addition of more alkali did not give any precipitate and the solution was light yellow in colour and showed fluorescence under UV light indicating the presence of fulvic acid. From a portion of this solution chloride and phosphate ions were removed as their insoluble silver salts and the material in it was designated as fulvic acid C.

Barium fulvates were further purified by repeated precipitations from acid solutions by addition of sodium hydroxide. The precipitates were isolated over a narrow range of pH values. To determine the homogeneity of the isolated material a solution of barium fulvate A was mixed with an acetate buffer (pH 4.8) when the

material was precipitated. The supernatant solution did not show any fluorescence under UV light. With barium fulvate B in borate buffer (pH 8) same behaviour was observed and the supernatant solution did not contain any fulvic acid. The crude (unfractionated) fulvic acid on circular paper chromatography separated into three bands. The purified materials gave single bands the slowest and fastest moving bands of the crude material corresponding to fraction A and C respectively; the middle one corresponded to fraction B. Electrophoresis of fraction A and B using thin layer silica gel plates and acetate (pH 4.8) and borate (pH 8) buffers, was carried out. At pH 4.8 fraction A did not move whereas the other fraction gave a single spot away from the starting line. Fraction B did not move in the borate buffer while fraction A gave a single spot. These results conclusively show that purified fulvic acids A and B were homogeneous.

Fraction C passed through dialysis bag and had strong fluorescence under UV light characteristic of fulvic acid. The material could not be precipitated out of its solution and the titration curve indicated it to be a strong acid. The yield of this fraction was low and no investigations could be attempted on it.

The titration curve of crude fulvic acid in presence of barium chloride has two distinct inflexion points, one at pH 4.5-4.8 and the other at pH 7.75-8. In between these two pH values there is no inflexion indicating that the precipitation process is not continuous. But it was found that after the precipitation of Ba-fulvate at pH 4.8 there was a continuous consumption of alkali by the remaining material with some buffer action as it was observed that the pH of the solution was lower than that expected with the amount of alkali added. This discontinuous fractional precipitation of fulvic acid suggests the possibility of at least two kinds of molecules, one containing major proportion of carboxyl groups and the other phenolic groups; the former one must have been precipitated at a lower pH and the latter at higher pH. The purified fulvic acid fractions A and B on potentiometric titration gave prominent inflexion at pH values corresponding to their precipitation points. The other one was minor. This is due to predominance

of carboxylic or phenolic groups in the molecule. Taking advantage of these characteristics it has been possible to separate the fulvic acid into three homogeneous fractions whose chromatographic and electrophoretic mobilities are different.

The sugars and amino acids detected in the hydrolyzates of fractions A and B are given in Table 2. Fraction A contains eleven amino acids and five sugars whereas fraction B contains nine amino acids and only three sugars. If sugars and amino acids are associated with fulvic acid and not integral part of it as has been assumed earlier¹⁷, it is not possible to obtain a single spot during electrophoresis of these purified substances in different buffers. So, it is conclusively shown that sugars and amino acids are artifacts of the fulvic acid molecules and that the two kinds of isolated and homogeneous fulvic acid fractions have some differences in their molecular architecture especially in the composition of sugars and amino acids.

Fulvic acid A was subjected to further studies to examine the sugar components. To remove the carbohydrate portion selectively from the material an enzyme "hemicellulase" was used. After the action of enzyme the fulvic acid was precipitated and was separated at the centrifuge. The enzyme-degraded fulvic acid on electrophoresis moved as a single spot. A portion of it on hydrolysis followed by paper chromatography did not show the presence of any sugar indicating that all the sugars in the material were removed by the enzyme. From the electrophoretic mobilities of the enzyme-degraded material it can be concluded that fulvic acid molecule is not degraded into small fragments which is only possible if the sugar moieties are joining two or more portions of the molecule containing aromatic rings; the sugar units are present as side chains joined to fulvic acid by glycosidic linkages.

The supernatant solution containing sugars, on paper chromatographic examination, gave spots corresponding to galactose, arabinose and a slow moving oligosaccharide. The mixture was separated on Whatman-No. 3MM filter papers into its components. The oligosaccharide moved as a single substance on electrophoresis and had $[\alpha]_D^{30} + 52^\circ$. It was found to contain galactose, arabinose, xylose, mannose, galacturonic acid and a small amount of an aldobiouronic acid. On mild acid hydrolysis followed by paper chromatographic examination galactose, arabinose, xylose and the aldobiouronic acid was detected. The aldobiouronic acid had mannose and galacturonic acid as component sugars. The oligosaccharide was reduced with sodium borohydride and the resulting product was hydrolysed. Paper chromatographic examination of the hydrolyzate using aniline oxalate as spray reagent showed the presence of galactose, xylose and the aldobiouronic acid indicating that arabinose formed the reducing end.

The methyl ester-methyl glycoside of the oligosaccharide on periodate oxidation consumed 2.1 moles of periodate liberating one mole of formic acid per 4.8 moles of anhydrohexose. These results indicate that the oligosaccharide contains five sugar units that are joined through 1→3 linkages. The periodate-oxidised

product on hydrolysis gave galactose, arabinose, xylose and mannose besides smaller aldehydes expected from a periodate-oxidised product.

To establish the sequence of sugar units in the oligosaccharide it was subjected to Barry's degradation¹⁸. After the first periodate oxidation the product was found to contain galactose, mannose and xylose resistant to oxidant. On Barry's degradation followed by second periodate oxidation mannose and galactose were cleaved leaving behind only intact xylose. From these results the structure of the oligosaccharide is as follows :

From these results it can be concluded that these sugar moieties viz., galactose, arabinose and the oligosaccharide containing five sugar units are present in fulvic acid A. But it was not possible to say whether all these units belonged to the same oligosaccharide or they were individually linked to the fulvic acid molecules through glycosidic linkages as the enzyme used was non-specific. The results of the present study do not indicate the site in the fulvic acid molecule to which the sugar units are joined.

Experimental

Paper chromatography was carried out by descending method using Whatman No. 1 papers and the following solvent systems (v/v) :

- (A) ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8:2:1),
- (B) n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4:1:5) upper layer,
- (C) ethyl acetate : pyridine : acetic acid : water (5:5:1:3),
- (D) ethyl acetate : acetic acid : water (9:2:2),
- (E) phenol-saturated with water,
- (F) n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4:1.2:2.8).

Spray reagents used for developing the chromatograms were :

- (a) alkaline silver nitrate solution,
- (b) saturated solution of aniline oxalate in water,
- (c) 0.2% solution of ninhydrin in butanol,
- (d) UV light was used to detect humic substances as they show fluorescence.

Unless otherwise stated all evaporations were carried out in vacuo at 40°. All values of specific rotations are at equilibrium. The enzyme "hemicellulase" was obtained from Koch-Light Laboratories, Colnbrook, Bucks, England.

Extraction and fractionation of humus acids : The soils have been collected from a layer 0"-6" below the surface near Dehradun, India (altitude 660 m) They were acidic (pH 5.2) and noncalcareous and contained plenty of roots ; the organic matter content was 5.5%. The humus was isolated by extracting the soil (500 g.) with mixture (1 l.) of solutions of Na-pyrophosphate and sodium hydroxide (pH 13). The supernatant obtained after keeping the solution overnight, was centrifuged and the crude humic acid was precipitated

out from the centrifugate by acidifying it with HCl to pH 2-3. The precipitate isolated at the centrifuge:

The deep yellow coloured supernatant was treated with a solution of barium chloride to convert fulvic acid into its barium salt. When pH of the solution was raised from 4.5-4.8 by adding a dilute solution of caustic soda a buff coloured precipitate of Ba-fulvate (fraction A) was obtained. It was centrifuged and from the supernatant a yellow coloured precipitate of Ba-fulvate (fraction B) was obtained at pH 8. It was again centrifuged. The supernatant was light yellow in colour and

times and finally the fulvic acid fraction was isolated as solid; yield: A, 1.5 g. ; B, 0.95 g.

To fulvic acid A (55 mg.) dissolved in water (20 ml), BaCl₂ was added to convert it into barium salt. The clear solution was added to 50 ml of acetate buffer (pH 4.8). The fulvic acid precipitated out completely and the supernatant did not show any fluorescence under UV light. Fulvic acid B behaved similarly with borate buffer (pH 8). In this case also the supernatant solution did not show fluorescence. Both the acids were subjected to electrophoresis using thin layer silica plates. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ELECTROPHORETIC STUDIES OF FULVIC ACID FRACTIONS

Fulvic acid fraction	Buffer (pH)	Time (hrs.)	Initial current (mA)	Final current (mA)	Potential gradient (V/cm)	Mobility of spots (cms.)
A	Acetate, 4.8	3	2.5	14.5	9.3	No movement
B	Acetate, 4.8	3	2.5	14.5	9.3	6.5(towards anode)
A	Borate, 8.0	3	4.0	8.0	9.3	3.3(towards anode)
B	Borate, 8.0	3	4.0	8.0	9.3	No movement
Hemicellulase-treated fraction A	Borate, 8.0	2.5	4.0	8.0	7.4	4.2(towards cathode)

had fluorescence under UV light. Further increase in pH did not give any precipitate. A portion of this solution containing fraction C, was treated with Ag₂CO₃ to remove the chloride and pyrophosphate ions.

The precipitate A and B were dialysed against distilled water for six days. Fulvic acid was prepared fresh before use by passing an aqueous suspension of Ba-fulvate through Amberlite IR-120(H). The supernatant (C) was also converted to its H-form by passing through Amberlite IR-120(H) column. The material passed through dialysis bag.

Purification of fractions A and B: Dialysed Ba-fulvates A and B were dissolved in dilute HCl and the pH of the solutions was raised gradually by adding a dilute sodium hydroxide solution. Just before the precipitating pH any insoluble material that formed, was removed at the centrifuge and the fulvic acid fraction was precipitated. It was isolated in the usual way and this precipitation process was repeated three more

The crude fulvic acid, containing fractions A, B and C and the individual fractions were subjected to circular paper chromatographic studies using the solvent (F). It was found that the crude material separated into three bands and the purified ones gave single bands: fulvic acid A corresponded to slow moving band B to the middle one and C to the fast moving one.

Potentiometric studies: Equal amounts (42.5 mg) of the three fractions of fulvic acid were titrated potentiometrically using 0.128 N caustic soda solution. In another set of experiments the crude fulvic acid was taken in different tubes each containing 193.2 mg of the crude material in 5 ml water. Saturated BaCl₂ solution (0.5 ml.) and different quantities of 0.128 N caustic soda solution (from 2.5 ml to 11.5 ml) were added to each. The tubes were kept for three days with occasional shaking and the precipitated material was removed off at the centrifuge. The pH of each of the supernatant was recorded. The results are graphically represented in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of the different fulvic acids

The fulvic acids A and B (50 mg each) were separately hydrolysed by heating with 6 *N* HCl for 24 hrs at boiling water bath temperature to release amino acids and with *N* H₂SO₄ for 12 hrs at the same temperature for obtaining sugars. The solutions were neutralised with Ag₂CO₃ and BaCO₃ respectively and the neutral hydrolysates were subjected to paper chromatographic examination. For amino acids solvents (B) and (E) and spray reagent (c) were used and for sugars solvents (A) and (C) and spray reagent (a) and (b) were used. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SUGARS AND AMINO ACID CONTENT OF FULVIC ACID FRACTIONS A AND B

Fraction	Sugars	Amino acids
A	Galactose, mannose, xylose, arabinose and galacturonic acid	Lysine, arginine, aspartic acid, glycine, alanine, serine, glutamic acid, valine, tryptophane, Leucine and one unidentified spot.
B	Galactose, mannose and galacturonic acid	Lysine, arginine, glycine, alanine, serine, glutamic acid, valine, tryptophane and one unidentified spot.

Fulvic acid A (500 mg) was hydrolysed with *N* sulphuric acid and after usual treatments the hydrolyzate containing sugars were separated into its component sugars on thick filter papers. The homogeneous fractions were characterised through their specific rotations to be D—galactose, D—mannose, D—xylose, D—galacturonic acid and L—arabinose.

Enzymic degradation of fulvic acid A : Fulvic acid A (736.5 mg) was suspended in acetate buffer (pH 4.9, 50 ml) and 2.2 mg of hemicellulase were added to it. The solution was incubated at 37° for 95 hours. The reaction mixture was then heated in a boiling water bath for 5 minutes to deactivate the enzyme. The solution was centrifuged and the supernatant was treated with barium hydroxide solution to precipitate the residual fulvic acid which was isolated at the centrifuge. Free fulvic acid was regenerated by treating the Ba-salt with Amberlite IR-120 (H) resin. It was subjected to electrophoresis under the conditions mentioned in Table 1. The material was moved as a single spot. On hydrolysis with *N* H₂SO₄ followed by neutralisation and centrifugation gave the hydrolysate which on paper chromatographic examination, did not give spot corresponding to any sugar.

The solution left after precipitation of fulvic acid, was concentrated and on paper chromatographic examination in solvents (B) and (D) gave spots corresponding to galactose, arabinose and a slow moving oligosaccharide. The mixture of sugars was separated on Whatman No. 3MM filter papers using solvent (D) and the oligosaccharide isolated; yield 22 mg. The oligosaccharide was subjected to paper electrophoresis using borate buffer (pH 9.4) and a potential gradient of 9.2 v/cm. After 2.5 hours the paper was removed, dried in air and then sprayed with alkaline silver nitrate reagent. Only one spot, 2 cm from the base line towards the cathode, was detected.

The oligosaccharide, $[\alpha]_D^{30} 52^\circ$ (c, 0.44 in water,) was hydrolysed with *N* H₂SO₄ for 10 hours in a boiling water bath. The hydrolysate was neutralised (BaCO₃), deionised with IR-120 (H) resin and then concentrated to a syrup. Paper chromatographic examination of it using solvents (A), (B) and (C) showed the presence of galactose, arabinose, xylose and an aldobiouronic acid. Drastic hydrolysis of the oligosaccharide followed by usual treatments and chromatographic examination gave spots corresponding to galactose, mannose, arabinose, xylose, galacturonic acid and a faint spot of aldobiouronic acid. The material (2 mg) in water was treated with NaBH₄ (10 mg) for 6 hours at room temperature. After usual treatments followed by hydrolysis and chromatographic examination using solvents (B) and (C) and aniline oxalate as spray reagent it gave spots corresponding to galactose, xylose and aldobiouronic acid.

The oligosaccharide (3 mg) was refluxed with 1% methanolic hydrogen chloride (10 ml) for 6 hrs on a hot water bath. The solution was evaporated *in vacuo* over potassium hydroxide till it was free from acid; yield 2 mg. The methyl ester-methyl glycoside of the oligosaccharide was then subjected to periodate oxidation studies at 3° in dark. The kinetics of this reaction were followed spectrophotometrically. One mole of anhydrohexose consumed 0.42 moles of the oxidant in 16 hours; in the same time one mole of formic acid was liberated per 4.8 moles of such unit. The periodate-oxidised material on hydrolysis and paper chromatographic examination gave spots corresponding to galactose, mannose, arabinose and xylose besides other smaller aldehydes expected from a periodate-oxidised product.

Barry's degradation of oligosaccharide : In a separate experiment the material (5 mg) was treated with .04 *M* sodium metaperiodate (3 ml) and the mixture was kept for 16 hrs in dark at 3°. The iodate and periodate ions were removed as their insoluble barium salts (bromothymol blue as indicator) and the clear supernatant was deionised with Amberlit I. R. 120(H) resin. A small part of the material in it was hydrolysed with *N* H₂SO₄ (5 ml) for 8 hrs in a boiling water bath. The hydrolysate after usual treatments, was concentrated and then subjected to paper chromatographic examination using solvent (B). Spots corresponding to galactose, mannose, xylose, and other smaller aldehydes were detected.

The remaining material of the periodate-oxidised product was dissolved in 45% ethanol (5 ml) and refluxed with phenyl hydrazine (0.1 ml) and acetic acid (0.1 ml) for 1.5 hours on a steam bath. The reaction mixture was evaporated to dryness and then taken up with water. The aqueous solution was extracted exhaustively with ether and the aqueous phase was concentrated to ca 1 ml. To this solution 1 ml of 0.04 *M* sodium metaperiodate solution was added and the reactions were allowed to proceed in dark at 3° for 24 hrs. The iodate and periodate ions were removed as described earlier and the second periodate-oxidised product was hydrolysed with *N*-sulphuric acid. After usual treatments the hydrolyzate was examined paper chromatographically using solvents (A) and (B). Xylose was the only sugar detected on paper chromatograms.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee for his keen interest and helpful suggestions in this work. The help of Dr. S. Samajpati and Mr. B.P. Chatterjee in some of the experiments is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. D. O. ROBINSON, W. P. MARTIN and J. B. PAGE., *Ohio. Agric. Expt. Sta. Bull.*, 1951, 705, 18 (69th Ann. Rept.).
2. C. B. COULSON, R. I. DAVIES and E. J. A. KHAN., *Soil Sci.*, 1959, 88, 191.
3. T. HAYASHI and T. NAGAI., *J. Fac. Agric. Tottori Univ.*, 1955, 2, 55.
4. F. SCHEFFER and B. ULRICH., *Humus und Humus dungung, Stuttgart Enke*, 1960.
5. S. SINGH and P. SINGH., *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1960, 29A, 378.
6. I. V. TYURIN., *Trudy Pochvy. Inst. Dokuchaeva*, 1940, 23, 23.
7. W. G. C. FORSYTH., *Biochemi. J.*, 1950, 46, 141.
8. T. HAYASHI and T. NAGAI., *Soil and Plant Food, Tokyo*, 1960, 5, 153.
9. E. SCHLICHTING, *Z. Pfl. Ernahr. Dung*, 1953, 61, 97, 193.
10. M. M. KONONOVA, N. P. BELCHIKOVA and V. K. NIKIFOROV., *Soviet Soil Sci.*, 1959, 285.
11. W. FLAIG, VERHANDL., II U IV, *Komm. Ins. Bodenk Ges.*, 1958, 2.
12. G. FERRARI and G. DELL AGNOLA., *Soil Sci.*, 1963, 96, 418.
13. G. FERRARI, G. DELL AGNOLA and A. MAGGIONI., *Transaction of International Symposium, "Humus et Planta IV"*, Prague, 1967.
14. J. N. LADD and J. H. A. BULTER., *Aust. J. Soil Res.*, 1966, 4, 41-54.
15. F. POSPISIL, *Vedecke Prace Ustredniho Vyzkumneho Ustavu Rostlinne Vyroby V Praze-Ruzyni*, 1965, 8, 171.
16. F. POSPISIL, *Transaction of the International Symposium, "Humus et Planta IV"* Prague, 1967.
17. S. K. BANERJEE, C. V. N. RAO and S. K. MUKHERJEE., *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1971, 19, 87.
18. V. C. BARRY., *Nature*, 1943, 152, 537.